

Assessment of the JEFF-4.0 Nuclear Data Library on the Sodium-Cooled Fast Reactor Superphénix

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of nuclear data updates from JEFF-3.3 to JEFF-4.0 on the sodium-cooled fast reactor Superphénix. The Serpent 2 code is used to calculate neutronic parameters such as critical eigenvalue, isothermal temperature coefficient, expansion component and Doppler coefficient. The results are validated and verified with experimental data and with the results from the literature. The results indicate that JEFF-4.0 tends to give lower k-eff values relative to earlier libraries. JEFF-4.0 also demonstrates good agreement with measured values for the isothermal temperature coefficient, expansion component and Doppler coefficient, showing the improvement in the accuracy of resonance-sensitive nuclides compared to JEFF-3.3. Furthermore, the sensitivity analysis has been performed with Serpent 2 on the multiplication factor by perturbing the basic cross sections. The sensitivity analysis shows that there is no significant difference in the integrated sensitivity coefficients between JEFF-3.3 and JEFF-4.0. The accuracy of major actinide data remains highly influential on k-eff predictions. Among non-fuel materials, iron shows the most significant impact on k-eff sensitivity, primarily through inelastic scattering and capture reactions.

Keywords: JEFF-4.0, SPX, SFR, Sensitivity, Serpent

1. INTRODUCTION

Criticality plays an important role in accurately predicting the neutronic characteristics of a reactor. These calculations rely on the nuclear data. Therefore, the impact of updated nuclear data on neutronics characteristics must be evaluated before incorporating such updates into practical applications, including reactor core design and various safety evaluations. The Nuclear Energy Agency Data Bank has released the latest version of the Joint Evaluated Fission and Fusion (JEFF) nuclear data library, JEFF-4.0, in June 2025 [1], following the release of JEFF-3.3 nuclear data library (JEFF-3.3) in 2017 [2].

This update introduced the improvement over JEFF-3.3 in modelling and simulation performance for both light water reactors and advanced reactors. Additionally, the neutron-induced reaction data in the JEFF-4.0 differ on many counts from those in JEFF-3.3. Major changes were made to the major actinides ²³⁵U, ²³⁸U and ²³⁹Pu in the resonance region and in the fast region, where new physics models were introduced [1]. These changes affect the neutron spectrum in fast reactor systems, leading to the change in results of criticality calculations for fast spectrum reactors.

The goal of this study is to assess the effect of nuclear data updates from the JEFF-3.3 to JEFF-4.0 on static sodium-cooled fast reactors (SFRs) calculations. The static neutronic calculations are performed for startup core of the Superphénix reactor (SPX). The simulation are verified and validated against the calculated values and experimental data from published literature to ensure the accuracy of modeling. The multiplication factor (k-eff) values calculated in Serpent [3] using the JEFF-3.3 and JEFF-4.0 are compared and evaluated for different core thermal configurations. Moreover, the sensitivity analysis is conducted to assess the effects of nuclear data updates to understand its influence on the static

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calculations. Energy-dependent sensitivities of k-eff to cross sections (XSs) are also investigated for a full understanding of these changes.

This paper consists of 4 sections. After given introduction (Section 1), Section 2 provides calculation geometries, calculation code, and nuclear data libraries for calculations. Section 3 presents the calculation results and discussion. Finally, Section 4 concludes the paper.

2. SIMULATION DESCRIPTION

2.1. Simulation Code and Nuclear Data

In this study, Serpent version 2.2.1 [3] (Serpent) was used to conduct the criticality and sensitivity calculations for the SPX. Serpent was developed at the VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland as a multi-purpose, three-dimensional, continuous-energy Monte Carlo particle transport code. The code has been widely adopted for reactor physics for tasks such as core design, fuel cycle studies, shielding analysis, and safety evaluations.

Sensitivity analysis in Serpent is implemented using adjoint weighting, calculated via the Iterated Fission Probability (IFP) method [4]. The IFP approach enables efficient estimation of sensitivity coefficients even in large and heterogeneous reactor configurations, without requiring explicit adjoint simulations. This version is capable of computing sensitivity coefficients; however, it does not support direct uncertainty propagation.

For the nuclear data libraries JEFF-3.1.1 [5], JEFF-3.3, and JEFF-4.0 were used. Serpent uses XS data files in the ACE format [6]. The ACE formatted files for JEFF-3.3, and JEFF-4.0 were generated using the nuclear data processing code NJOY [7] with the XS at 300 K, 453 K, 600 K, 673 K, 900 K, and 1500 K. For calculations with the JEFF-3.1.1, the ACE files included in the Serpent package were used. These ACE files are available at 300 K, 600 K, 900 K, and 1500 K. For criticality calculations, Monte Carlo calculations were performed with one million histories per cycle, 1000 active cycles, and 100 inactive cycles. Due to the memory consumption of sensitivity calculations, the sensitivity calculations were conducted with 100000 histories per cycle, 4000 active cycles, and 516 inactive cycles. However, all standard deviations of k-eff values are less than 10 pcm, which was small enough to discern differences in k-eff due to nuclear data library updates. Unresolved resonance probability table sampling is turned on as well as on-the-fly Doppler broadening treatment.

2.2. Description of the Superphénix Core

The Superphénix sodium-cooled fast reactor was located in Creys-Malville, France, and contained 358 fuel subassemblies and approximately 5.7 tons of plutonium [8]. Construction began in 1977, with first criticality achieved in 1985 with a thermal power of 2990 MW and an electric power of 1242 MW. The SPX core follows a conventional SFR design, featuring MOX fuel subassemblies with varying fissile content, surrounded by a breeder zone of fertile uranium oxide. Subassemblies are arranged in a triangular lattice and enclosed in hexagonal wrappers, with axial breeding zones integrated into the fuel pins. During its operational period, SPX generated extensive experimental data, contributing significantly to the understanding of large fast reactor behavior. A benchmark [9] has been developed to validate neutronics and thermal-hydraulic simulation tools under both steady-state and transient conditions. The benchmark includes detailed core specifications, reference solutions, and comparative results from seven modeling approaches, based on the reactor's start-up configuration.

The benchmark core model is a simplified version of the SPX start-up core. Three fuel compositions are defined: inner and outer core fissile MOX fuels with different enrichment levels, and a single fertile UO₂ fuel used in all breeder zones. The core consists 190 and 168 subassemblies (SAs) in the inner and outer fuel regions, respectively; 224 breeder SAs; and 21 control and 3 shutdown SAs. The SA pitch at 20°C is 17.9 cm, while the fuel pin pitch is 0.98 cm for fissile and 1.69 cm for fertile fuel pins. The active fuel height is 160 cm. All structural components are modeled using 316Ti stainless steel, and helium-4 fills the voids inside fuel and absorber pin claddings. The absorber SA consists of a bundle of 31 absorber pins, each containing boron carbide enriched to 90% in boron-10. Two types of absorber SA are used: control (CSD) and shutdown (DSD). The main difference between them is in the length of the

absorber region, which is 160 cm for CSD and 100 cm for DSD. Multiple thermal states are considered, with temperature-dependent adjustments to geometry and material density. Detailed descriptions of the geometry, materials, and experiments can be found in [9] [10] [11] [12].

3. CALCULATION RESULTS

3.1. Verification and validation

This section presents the verification and validation of SPX simulation results against reference data available in the literature. A set of core configurations has been considered in criticality calculations, as listed in Table I. These cases differ in geometry and XS temperatures, reflecting various thermal conditions. To ensure the model accurately reproduces benchmark solutions across different core states, temperature-dependent adjustments were applied to material dimensions and densities. Additionally, the impact of nuclear data updates in the JEFF-4.0 library on the k-eff was evaluated. For all simulations, the positions of CSD and DSD SAs were fixed in the fully withdrawn state. The CSD SAs are located above the fissile fuel region, while DSD SAs are positioned above the upper axial blanket. Reference solutions used for verification were obtained using Serpent with the JEFF-3.1.1 nuclear data library, as reported in [9] [10]. Experimental values are also available in [9] [12] [13].

Table I. SPX core configurations in criticality calculations.

Case ID	Temperature for XS / geometry (Kelvin)		
	Fissile	Fertile	Non-fuel
1	300/293	300/293	300/293
2	300/453	300/453	300/453
3	453/453	453/453	453/453
4	300/673	300/673	300/673
5	600/673	600/673	600/673
6	600/673	600/673	300/673
7	673/673	673/673	673/673
8	900/673	900/673	900/673
9	1500/1500	900/900	673/673

Table II summarizes the reference k-eff from previous benchmark studies [10] and compares them with the results obtained from current simulations using various nuclear data libraries. The values calculated using JEFF-3.1.1 show good agreement with the reference data. In most cases, the differences remain within two standard deviations, except for cases 3, 8, and 9. Cases 3 and 8 slightly exceed this range, though the deviations are minor and likely caused by small differences in modeling assumptions, nuclear data, or code versions. Case 9 shows a more noticeable deviation of approximately 83 pcm, which is attributed to a difference in the outer fissile material number density at 1500 Kelvin (K). The number density used in the current simulation differs from that reported in reference [10]. When the same value is applied, the deviation reduces to less than 10 pcm. Overall, the comparison in Table II demonstrates that the simulation results are closely aligned with the reference data. In subsequent analyses, the discrepancies attributed to the use of different versions of the JEFF nuclear data library are presented.

Compared with the reference data, the results obtained using JEFF-3.3 show larger deviations than those using JEFF-3.1.1. In cases 1 and 2, the XSs temperatures stay at 300 K, while the geometry temperatures increase from 293 K in case 1 to 453 K in case 2. The differences in these two cases are similar, with JEFF-3.3 results being less than 20 pcm lower. When the XS temperature is increased to 453 K, the difference between case 2 and case 3 increases from 12 pcm in case 2 to 39 pcm in case 3. This may be due to the lack of pre-generated XS data at 453 K in the calculation of reference solution. When the XS data is unavailable at that temperature, the Serpent code uses an analytical Doppler-broadening treatment to adjust the XS data for JEFF-3.1.1. Cases 4, 6, and 7 show good agreement between JEFF-3.3

and the reference, with differences around two standard deviations. Case 5, however, shows a noticeable positive difference of up to 25 pcm. This seems to be caused by the XS data for the non-fuel materials. Cases 5 and 6 are the same except for the temperature of the non-fuel material XSs, e.g., 600 K in case 5 and 300 K in case 6. While case 6 matches the reference well, the higher temperature in case 5 increases the difference. Case 8 shows a similar pattern to case 5, suggesting that the increased temperature of the non-fuel material XSs may also be the cause for the difference in k-eff. In case 9, the deviation of a 74 pcm shortfall is mainly due to a mismatch in the number density of the outer fissile material. By using the same number density as in the reference [9], the JEFF-3.3 result slightly overestimates the k-eff value.

The calculated values using JEFF-4.0 show a noticeable deviation of the k-eff value compared to the reference data. In cases 1 through 4, the underestimations are slightly above 100 pcm, while in cases 5 through 9, the differences are less than 50 pcm. A comparison between cases 4 and 6 indicates that increasing the temperatures of the fertile and fissile material XSs reduces the discrepancy from -110 pcm to -49 pcm. While cases 5 and 6 are identical except for the temperature of the non-fuel material XSs, the difference relative to the reference remains nearly the same. This suggests that the main factor contributing to the reduction in discrepancy, from approximately 100 pcm to approximately 50 pcm, is the increase in temperature of the fissile and fertile material XSs.

Table II. Comparison between reference solutions and calculated values.

Case ID	k-eff, reference	Absolute difference in pcm ($\pm 1\sigma$)		
	JEFF-3.1.1	JEFF-3.1.1	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-4.0
1	1.04365	2 (± 2)	-19 (± 2)	-112 (± 2)
2	1.04246	5 (± 2)	-12 (± 2)	-111 (± 2)
3	1.03670	10 (± 2)	-39 (± 2)	-122 (± 2)
4	1.04080	2 (± 2)	-5 (± 2)	-110 (± 2)
5	1.03053	1 (± 2)	25 (± 4)	-47 (± 2)
6	1.03139	2 (± 2)	-3 (± 4)	-49 (± 2)
7	1.02886	3 (± 2)	1 (± 6)	-38 (± 2)
8	1.02483	9 (± 2)	26 (± 2)	-35 (± 2)
9	1.01903	-83 (± 2)	-74 (± 2)	-109 (± 2)

Table III presents a comparison between the calculated reactivity values using the JEFF-3.3 and JEFF-4.0 nuclear data libraries and the reference (measured) values. Cases 3, 7, and 9 correspond to the cold, hot zero power (HZP), and hot full power (HFP) states, respectively. The calculated values show the same trend as the measurements, reactivity decreases with increasing temperature. This reduction in reactivity is attributed to Doppler broadening and thermal expansion effects, both of which lead to a negative reactivity feedback as temperature increases. However, both JEFF-3.3 and JEFF-4.0 calculations underestimate the measured reactivity values and the underestimation progressively increases with temperature, from the cold state to the HFP. Furthermore, the discrepancies are slightly larger with JEFF-4.0 than with JEFF-3.3.

Table III. Reactivity comparison of calculated results with measured values.

Case ID	Measured reactivity (pcm)	Calculated reactivity (pcm)		Absolute difference (pcm)	
		JEFF-3.3	JEFF-4.0	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-4.0
3 (cold)	3710	3504 (± 2)	3426 (± 2)	-206	-284
7 (HZP)	3079	2806 (± 4)	2769 (± 2)	-273	-310
9 (HFP)	2070	1796 (± 2)	1762 (± 2)	-294	-328

Table IV presents the experimental and calculated values of the thermal feedback components affecting the reactivity of the SPX reactor. The isothermal temperature coefficient, expansion component, and Doppler coefficient are all negative values. However, Table IV only presents the magnitudes of these coefficients for comparison. The calculated results show good agreement with the measurements, generally within one to two times the experimental uncertainty. However, some deviations are observed. The expansion component is underestimated, while the Doppler coefficient is overestimated in the calculations. This is reflected in the underestimation of reactivity values presented in Table III. It is important to note that several assumptions were made in this benchmark, including homogenization of the fuel temperature, simplified expansion models, and fuel enrichment values, which may all contribute to the observed discrepancies.

Table IV. Thermal feedbacks comparison of calculated results with measured values.

Case ID	Measurement	Calculation		Absolute difference	
		JEFF-3.3	JEFF-4.0	JEFF-3.3	JEFF-4.0
Isothermal temperature coefficient (pcm/°C)	2.87 (± 0.14)	2.87 (± 0.02)	2.99 (± 0.01)	0.00	0.12
Expansion component (pcm/°C)	0.74 (± 0.15)	0.67 (± 0.01)	0.69 (± 0.01)	-0.07	-0.05
Doppler coefficient (pcm)	1180 (± 118)	1341 (± 4)	1299 (± 4)	161	119

3.2. Sensitivity results

In this section, the sensitivity of individual nuclides to the k-eff at different reactor conditions (Cold, HZP, and HFP) is investigated. The sensitivity profiles and the integrated sensitivity coefficients (ISCs) were obtained using the Serpent. The sensitivity profile illustrates how each reaction XS contributes to the k-eff at different incident neutron energies, while the ISC quantifies the cumulative sensitivity by summing contributions over all the energies. This study evaluates the sensitivity of k-eff to changes in the nuclear data library from JEFF-3.3 to JEFF-4.0. However, it does not account for uncertainties inherent in the nuclear data itself. The sensitivity analysis includes perturbations of the elastic scattering, inelastic scattering, neutron capture, fission, and (n,xn) reaction XSs for all nuclides present in the reactor core. Table V, Table VI, and Table VII present the six highest ISC values for fuel materials and the three highest for non-fuel materials across the different core states, using both JEFF-3.3 and JEFF-4.0. The most significant contributions to k-eff sensitivity come from fission in ²³⁹Pu and capture in ²³⁸U. In contrast, ISCs for non-fuel materials are considerably lower, with the highest values arising from inelastic scattering and capture in ⁵⁶Fe. Minor differences in ISC, within the statistical uncertainties, values are observed between the two libraries.

Table V. Reactions with largest values of the ISC for k-eff at cold state.

JEFF-3.3		JEFF-4.0	
Isotope	ISC (%/%)	Isotope	ISC (%/%)
²³⁹ Pu (n, f)	0.5068 ± 1%	²³⁹ Pu (n, f)	0.5044 ± 1%
²³⁸ U (n, γ)	-0.2246 ± 1%	²³⁸ U (n, γ)	-0.2255 ± 1%
²³⁸ U (n, f)	0.0704 ± 1%	²³⁸ U (n, f)	0.0736 ± 1%
²³⁹ Pu (n, γ)	-0.0615 ± 1%	²³⁹ Pu (n, γ)	-0.0617 ± 1%
²⁴¹ Pu (n, f)	0.0599 ± 1%	²⁴¹ Pu (n, f)	0.0586 ± 1%
²³⁸ U inelastic	-0.0501 ± 1%	²³⁸ U inelastic	-0.0503 ± 1%
⁵⁶ Fe inelastic	-0.0160 ± 1%	⁵⁶ Fe inelastic	-0.0176 ± 1%

$^{56}\text{Fe} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0113 \pm 1\%$	$^{56}\text{Fe} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0121 \pm 1\%$
$^{58}\text{Ni} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0093 \pm 1\%$	$^{58}\text{Ni} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0090 \pm 1\%$

 Table VI. Reactions with largest values of the ISC for k -eff at HZP state.

JEFF-3.3		JEFF-4.0	
Isotope	ISC (%/%)	Isotope	ISC (%/%)
$^{239}\text{Pu} (n, f)$	$0.5079 \pm 1\%$	$^{239}\text{Pu} (n, f)$	$0.5073 \pm 1\%$
$^{238}\text{U} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.2297 \pm 1\%$	$^{238}\text{U} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.2250 \pm 1\%$
$^{238}\text{U} (n, f)$	$0.0731 \pm 1\%$	$^{238}\text{U} (n, f)$	$0.0745 \pm 1\%$
$^{239}\text{Pu} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0613 \pm 1\%$	$^{239}\text{Pu} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0592 \pm 1\%$
$^{241}\text{Pu} (n, f)$	$0.0596 \pm 1\%$	$^{241}\text{Pu} (n, f)$	$0.0586 \pm 1\%$
^{238}U inelastic	$-0.0527 \pm 1\%$	^{238}U inelastic	$-0.0516 \pm 1\%$
^{56}Fe inelastic	$-0.0171 \pm 1\%$	^{56}Fe inelastic	$-0.0182 \pm 1\%$
$^{56}\text{Fe} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0115 \pm 1\%$	$^{56}\text{Fe} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0122 \pm 1\%$
$^{58}\text{Ni} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0094 \pm 1\%$	$^{58}\text{Ni} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0090 \pm 1\%$

 Table VII. Reactions with largest values of the ISC for k -eff at HFP state.

JEFF-3.3		JEFF-4.0	
Isotope	ISC (%/%)	Isotope	ISC (%/%)
$^{239}\text{Pu} (n, f)$	$0.5151 \pm 1\%$	$^{239}\text{Pu} (n, f)$	$0.5126 \pm 1\%$
$^{238}\text{U} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.2242 \pm 1\%$	$^{238}\text{U} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.2253 \pm 1\%$
$^{238}\text{U} (n, f)$	$0.0724 \pm 1\%$	$^{238}\text{U} (n, f)$	$0.0755 \pm 1\%$
$^{241}\text{Pu} (n, f)$	$0.0603 \pm 1\%$	$^{241}\text{Pu} (n, f)$	$0.0589 \pm 1\%$
$^{239}\text{Pu} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0563 \pm 1\%$	$^{239}\text{Pu} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0562 \pm 1\%$
^{238}U inelastic	$-0.0530 \pm 1\%$	^{238}U inelastic	$-0.0530 \pm 1\%$
^{56}Fe inelastic	$-0.0164 \pm 1\%$	^{56}Fe inelastic	$-0.0187 \pm 1\%$
$^{56}\text{Fe} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0110 \pm 1\%$	$^{56}\text{Fe} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0118 \pm 1\%$
$^{58}\text{Ni} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0091 \pm 1\%$	$^{58}\text{Ni} (n, \gamma)$	$-0.0089 \pm 1\%$

Figure 1 and Figure 2 present the sensitivity profiles of k -eff to selected nuclide XSs at different core states, calculated using the JEFF-4.0 nuclear data library. The results are shown per unit lethargy width, based on the Serpent built-in energy group structure (Vitamin-J 175-group). In general, the sensitivity profiles across cold, HZP, and HFP conditions are consistent. However, a notable deviation is observed in the sensitivity of the neutron capture XS of ^{239}Pu . As the reactor temperature increases, the sensitivity to neutron capture in ^{239}Pu decreases. This trend is also reflected in the corresponding ISCs, as shown in Table V, Table VI, and Table VII.

Figure 1. Sensitivity profiles of the highest ISCs in fuel materials at different core states.

Figure 2. Sensitivity profiles of the highest ISCs in non-fuel materials at different core states.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, simulations of the SPX reactor were verified and validated against reference data available in the literature. The impact of the updated nuclear data library, JEFF-4.0, was evaluated in terms of its effect on key reactor physics parameters, including the k -eff, isothermal temperature coefficient, expansion component, and Doppler coefficient. Additionally, the sensitivity of JEFF-4.0 on the k -eff value was assessed through the perturbation of XSs.

The results indicate that JEFF-4.0 tends to result in lower k -eff values relative to earlier libraries such as JEFF-3.1.1 and JEFF-3.3. However, the discrepancies do not show a strong dependence on fuel temperature, a similar behavior is observed across both low and high temperature conditions. JEFF-4.0 also demonstrates good agreement with measured values for the isothermal temperature coefficient, expansion component, and Doppler coefficient. The JEFF-4.0 shows better Doppler coefficient accuracy than the JEFF-3.3, indicating enhanced reliability for resonance-sensitive nuclides, particularly for major actinides such as ^{235}U , ^{238}U , and ^{239}Pu , which play a critical role in fast reactor systems. The sensitivity analysis further shows that there is no significant difference in the ISCs between JEFF-3.3 and JEFF-4.0. The accuracy of major actinide data remains highly influential on the k -eff predictions.

Among non-fuel materials, iron shows the most significant impact on k-eff sensitivity, primarily through inelastic scattering and capture reactions. Future work will focus on evaluating the influence of JEFF-4.0 on k-eff behavior during burnup calculations, to assess its performance over the reactor's operational lifetime.

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